

Effects of Corporate Social Responsibility Initiatives on the Financial Performance of SMEs

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Abstract:

This study examines the effect of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives on the financial performance of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), focusing on their financial aspect rather than examining larger industries' CSR practices. A cross-sectional descriptive survey design was used for this study. A sample of 77 wholesalers and retailers from Santiago City owners or appointed representatives by the business owner responded, given that such a representative is a continuing employee with at least three years of service in the business. The study finds a strong positive relationship between CSR initiatives and the financial performance of SMEs,

wherein CSR initiatives serve as a business strategy to improve their business operations. It further suggests that CSR does not lead to financial gain but engagement in various economic, social, and environmental activities that significantly indirectly affect SMEs' financial performance. The paper discusses the role of CSR initiatives in SMEs' business strategies, highlighting their potential to enhance operations, financial performance, competitiveness, and revenue growth, contributing to the business industry, economics, and environment.

Keywords: *Corporate social responsibility, Financial performance, Retailer, Small and medium enterprises.*

Introduction

Business theory and practice have long held the belief that a firm's primary purpose is to maximize profit (David, 2012; Fiori et al., 2007). In Nigeria, corporations and societies are becoming more familiar with Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). However, within the first five years of operation, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have noticed a clear trend toward failure (Adebisi & Gbegi, 2013). These failures are partly a result of the numerous difficulties small businesses encounter that limit their expansion, including a lack of managerial, leadership, and marketing abilities that would give them a competitive edge. Furthermore, Okpara (2011) claimed that corruption, poor entrepreneurship policy implementation, and difficulty obtaining financing were to blame for Nigeria's small business failures, as businesses act unethically due to pressure to boost revenues and maintain competition.

Small business owners account for 97% of the economy, creating around 70% of Nigeria's jobs and wealth (Shehu et al., 2013). However, the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) asserts that 80% of SMEs fail to remain in operation for more than five years because some small business owners know little about the elements that can help a company survive for more than five years (Adebisi & Gbegi, 2013). Thus, the failure rate is concerning as small business owners in Nigeria employ 50% of the country's workforce (Atawodi & Ojeka, 2012) and generate around 70% of all new jobs (Apulu & Ige, 2011; Shehu et al., 2013).

In emerging and developed nations, small business owners have been crucial to economic progress (Boateng et al., 2013). Hence, regarding CSR, SMEs demonstrate the importance of entrepreneurship to the nation's economy (Ayanda & Laraba, 2011). The Nigerian economy's fundamental components, including families, communities, local governments, and nonprofit organizations, are all impacted if firms' unceasingly high failure rate in their first five years of operation continues (Obiwuru et al., 2011).

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) has recently received much attention in both academic studies and the business world, wherein businesses use it to acquire competitive advantage and attain a win-win situation with stakeholders, thereby creating the notion that is gradually gaining popularity in developing nations. However, it is only partially voluntary to implement it in a company setting because its potential advantages are understated, especially in Vietnam (Thanh et al., 2021).

The possible advantages of CSR still need to be fully addressed in the business world, primarily in Vietnam. Thus, the approach is not voluntary (Thanh et al., 2021). Furthermore, corporate social responsibility influences a firm's productivity, and consumers' purchasing intentions still influence its involvement because if a company or organization has a small customer base, it is likely to be challenging for it to fulfill the budgetary goals of the charity it has chosen (Yoon & Chung, 2018). The company's reputation gives it the responsibility to encourage customers to use its services or goods to meet the target of making a charitable contribution to the chosen charity. Additionally, suppose the firm has customers who value eco-friendly goods. In that case, such customers can convince other customers to support the business because, through the consummation of goods or services, those customers already support charities or the environment (The Elusive Green Consumer, 2022).

Bueno et al. (2019) have noticed a growth in the number of entities and corporate organizations engaging in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) for a myriad of benefits, wherein the most crucial factor is the ability to support the community where they operate and be open to societal demands thereby, CSR has demonstrated that some businesses addressed these considerations by allocating additional resources to CSR (Agan et al., 2016; Brammer & Millington, 2005; Lantos, 2001). However, management at some firms has objected, saying that further CSR spending is incompatible with efforts to increase profitability (Reverte et al., 2016). Given this argument, assessments of the economic effect of CSR need to be more

inaccurate (Lin et al., 2009). To justify the cost over the benefits a company can get from implementing different CSR programs, Russell (2018) identified the effect of CSR on the overall sustainability of businesses, considering the community to which they belong. Sanclemente-Téllez (2017) identified that the benefits of firms having CSR engagement are highly evident, namely that it gains positive public and business sustainability. Tax incentives and cost savings were also included as other benefits. In a broader area, businesses participating in CSR implementation have gained more patronage of their products and services and improved their public reputation (Sanclemente-Téllez, 2017).

Corporate Social responsibility has a fluid definition and can vary across corporate programs that benefit the community (Chandler & Werther, 2015; Jenkins, 2006; Longo et al., 2005). Konishi (2014) notes that CSR is crucial in responding to the problems and challenges of small and medium-sized business sectors to strengthen growth potential, effectiveness, and sustainability. Small businesses faced numerous challenges and failures, including needing more managerial, leadership, and marketing abilities (Adebisi & Gbegi, 2013; Gnounfougou & Niu, 2021). Companies can gain an advantage from being involved in CSR, which is knowing how they affect society, including but not limited to the economic and environmental aspects (Fernando, 2021).

CSR is associated with sustainability principles (Wu & Jin, 2022). It argues that every organization should make decisions based on their immediate and long-term impact on social and environmental factors rather than only financial ones. This decision should produce an overall positive impact on society (Spiliakos, 2018).

Sales performance management (SPM) is one of the most frequently used methods for tracking and managing the performance of sales representatives (Lee, 2022). Sales performance serves as a tool for overseeing the overall performance of a business operation (Groza, 2011; Lai, 2010; Tiep Le, 2021). Überseder et al.

(2013) explained that the better the sales performance, the better the business will run.

The research aims to determine the effects of corporate social responsibility initiatives on the financial performance of small and medium-sized enterprises in Santiago City. Many studies have been conducted focusing on the CSR programs and practices of the different industries, considering their size and how they influence the overall firm performance of these companies. However, they need more from the SMEs' standpoint. Additionally, the researcher finds that some articles should have considered the effect of CSR actions in each business function, such as the sales function of the business. To fill this gap, the researcher wants to determine the CSR initiatives of SMEs and their effects on their financial performance. This study will contribute to understanding the role of CSR initiatives, particularly in the financial performance of SMEs, to determine the relationship between the variables and why they are relevant in conducting a business.

Research Questions

The research aims to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the extent of involvement of the SMEs concerning corporate social responsibility initiatives?
2. To what extent do small and medium-sized enterprises agree on their financial performance?
3. What is the difference in the corporate social responsibility initiatives among small and medium-sized enterprises?
4. How do small and medium-sized enterprises' corporate social responsibility initiatives affect their financial performance?

Materials and Methods

A cross-sectional descriptive survey design was employed to determine the effect of CSR initiatives and SMEs' financial performance systematically because it is essential for obtaining data in a natural context within a short time

frame by determining if the other variables influence the variables but not as contingent on the existence of one to the other and in what setting the variable is directly affected (Bahta et al., 2020; Boru, 2018; Siedlecki, 2020; Waheed & Yang, 2018). The research design was appropriate since the researchers would like to study the extent of CSR actions and the financial performance of SMEs upon implementation to determine the variables' effects. This type is an appropriate research design because the variables are not manipulated, allowing the researcher to gather information on the variables at the individual level and determine the effects between them (Saunders et al., 2010).

The study was conducted in Santiago City, a first-class independent city (Santiago City Profile – PhilAtlas, n.d.). Santiago City is recognized as the commercial hub with an enormous growing number of SMEs, which has become the center of the Cagayan Valley (Cities and Municipalities Competitiveness Index, n.d.). The participants are the owners or any of the appointed representatives by the business owners of small and medium enterprises engaged in the wholesaling and retailing products in Santiago City. For the appointed representative's qualification, the business representative must be a continuing employee and have at least three years of service in the business. A total population of 121 wholesalers and retailers was utilized based on the Department of Trade and Industry data. The researchers aimed to administer the questionnaire to all the qualified participants; however, only 77 voluntarily participated, resulting in a 63.64% response rate. The demographic profile of the participants in terms of sex, age, and year of service is shown in the table below.

The research utilized questionnaires that had been adapted from prior studies. The questionnaire comprises 34 items designed to assess the financial performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and their level of CSR involvement. In part one, the participants' demographic profiles and business profiles in terms of the years in operation. Part II measures the corporate social responsibility initiatives comprising 22 items sourced from the

study by Guerrero-Villegas et al. (2018), Lindgreen et al. (2009), and Martinez-Conesa et al. (2017). The items were rated using a 5-point Likert scale, where 5 represents strongly agree, and 1 represents strongly disagree. Part III measures the financial performance of SMEs derived from the research conducted by Bustillo et al. (2022).

Table 1. Distribution of Participants According to Their Demographic Profile

Profile		n	%
Sex	Male	25	32.5
	Female	52	67.5
Age	18 yrs. old and below	0	0
	19-23yrs. old	12	15.6
	24-28 yrs. old	18	23.4
	29-33 yrs. old	18	23.4
	34-38 yrs. old	8	10.4
	39-43 yrs. old	9	11.7
	44-48 yrs. old	6	7.8
	49-53 yrs. old	1	1.3
	54-58 yrs. old	2	2.6
	59-63 yrs. old	1	1.3
Number of Years of Operation	3 yrs. and below	12	15.6
	4-6 yrs.	18	23.4
	7-9 yrs.	8	10.4
	10-12 yrs.	9	11.7
	13-15 yrs.	7	9.1
	16-18 yrs.	3	3.9
	19-21 yrs.	5	6.5
	22-24 yrs.	2	2.6
	25-27 yrs.	1	1.3
	28-30 yrs.	3	3.9
	31 yrs. and above	9	11.7

The questionnaire comprises 12 items that utilize a 7-point Likert scale where 1 means strongly disagree and 7 means strongly agree. An informed consent letter was attached to the survey questionnaire distributed to the participants. The researchers gathered the participants' answers to the survey questionnaire and evaluated each set to check if the participants responded to all the questions. The instrument with incomplete responses was discarded and not included in the data analysis.

After collecting all the survey questionnaires, the information was tallied and scored using Microsoft Excel. The tabulated data were analyzed and interpreted using Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 28. The data set on small and medium-sized enterprises' corporate social responsibility initiatives was analyzed using means and standard deviation. An Independent sample t-test was also used to identify the difference between the CSR initiatives of small and medium enterprises. Linear regression was utilized to determine the effect of small and medium-sized enterprises' corporate social responsibility initiatives on their financial performance.

In conformity with the Data Privacy Act, the participant's rights and privileges along with the study were most concerned. Data and information privacy and anonymity were maintained during this study. The researcher employed complete confidentiality about the participants and the provided data. The

researcher also ensured that the language used in the questionnaires was proper, clear, and acceptable. The participants were given complete information on the nature of the study through written informed consent before distributing the questionnaire. Also, the researcher acknowledged the works of other authors in this study through proper citation.

Results

The findings on the corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives and financial performance of small and medium-sized enterprises are presented to determine the effects of corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives on the financial performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Santiago, City.

The data on small and medium-sized enterprises' corporate social responsibility are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Level of SME's Corporate Social Responsibility Initiatives

Description	M	SD	Interpretation
1. Our company takes into account employees' interests in decision-making.	4.29	0.72	Strongly Agree
2. Our company helps employees balance their private and professional lives.	4.53	0.62	Strongly Agree
3. Our company's policies encourage employees to develop their skills and careers.	4.62	0.61	Strongly Agree
4. Our company recognizes the importance of stable employment for its employees and society (in the local area).	4.61	0.59	Strongly Agree
5. The managerial decisions related to the employees are usually fair.	4.61	0.59	Strongly Agree
6. Our company provides procedures that help ensure our employees' health and safety.	4.65	0.70	Strongly Agree
7. Our company incorporates the interests of our customers in our business decisions.	4.49	0.62	Strongly Agree
8. Our company provides full and accurate information about its products/services to its customers.	4.64	0.54	Strongly Agree
9. Customer satisfaction is highly important for our company.	4.79	0.44	Strongly Agree
10. Our company takes measures to prevent customer complaints.	4.71	0.48	Strongly Agree
11. Our company responds to customer complaints or inquiries.	4.64	0.51	Strongly Agree
12. Our company contributes to campaigns and projects that promote the well-being of society.	4.38	0.80	Strongly Agree
13. Our company has transparent relations with the local authorities.	4.43	0.72	Strongly Agree
14. Our company is considered part of the local community and is concerned with its development and the improvement of its infrastructure.	4.35	0.70	Strongly Agree
15. Our company encourages its employees to participate in voluntary work.	4.21	0.80	Strongly Agree
16. Financially support activities (arts, culture, sports) in our communities.	4.14	0.88	Agree

17. Stimulate economic development in the communities where we operate.	4.31	0.71	Strongly Agree
18. Our company incorporates environmental concerns in business decisions.	4.42	0.78	Strongly Agree
19. Our company participates in activities that aim to protect and improve the quality of the natural environment.	4.44	0.77	Strongly Agree
20. Takes government regulations about the environment beyond what the law requires.	4.62	0.54	Strongly Agree
21. Invest/be involved in saving energy.	4.45	0.70	Strongly Agree
22. Implements programs/involvement to reduce water consumption.	4.26	0.80	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.48		Strongly Agree

Note: M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation

Table 2 shows that the respondents strongly agree with the description that determines the CSR Initiatives of SMEs ($M = 4.48$, $SD = 0.18$). The respondents strongly agree that involvement in corporate social responsibility initiatives helps them avoid problems and attract and retain talent in their workforce. Moreover,

the respondents strongly agree that Customer satisfaction is essential for their company and that they financially support activities (arts, culture, sports) in their communities.

The SMEs' financial performance of small and medium-sized enterprises is shown below.

Table 3. Financial Performance of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises

Description	M	SD	Interpretation
1. The business is taking in more cash than it is spending.	5.62	0.93	Agree
2. The business has sufficient cash to manage its operations.	6.16	0.83	Strongly Agree
3. The business generates cash very well to fund its operating expenses and to pay its liabilities.	6.17	0.91	Strongly Agree
4. The business was able to increase production, which resulted in increased sales and profitability.	6.06	0.98	Agree
5. The business efficiently used resources to generate revenues above its expenses.	6.19	0.65	Strongly Agree
6. The business's ability to produce a return on investment based on its resources was good.	6.18	0.79	Strongly Agree
7. The pricing strategies employed were effective.	6.34	0.82	Strongly Agree
8. The promotional strategies employed delivered the expected results.	6.25	1.03	Strongly Agree
9. There is an increase in demand in the business.	5.97	1.08	Agree
10. The sales of the business increase.	5.79	1.04	Agree
11. The profit of the business increases.	5.87	1.02	Agree
12. The financial aspect of the business is in good shape.	6.05	0.90	Agree
Overall Mean	6.06		Agree

Note: M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation

Table 3 shows that the respondents agree that their financial performance is in good shape considering CSR initiatives ($M = 6.06$, $SD = 0.21$). The respondents agree that their business is taking in more cash than spending and strongly agree that it has sufficient cash to manage its operations. Also, the respondents

agree that the sales and profit of the business increase.

An Independent sample t-test was employed to determine the difference in the corporate social responsibility initiatives between small and medium-sized enterprises.

Table 4. Difference in CSR Initiatives Between Small and Medium-sized Enterprises

	Size	N	M	<i>t</i>	df	<i>p</i> -value
CSR Initiatives	Small	41	4.47	-0.21	75	0.834
	Medium	36	4.49			

Note: *N* = sample; *M* = mean; *SD* = standard deviation; *t* = value of *t*; *df* = degree of freedom; *p*-value = probability value

An Independent Sample T-test was conducted to compare the small and medium-sized enterprises' responses/assessments on Corporate Social Responsibility. The results indicated that small enterprises CSR initiatives (*M* = 4.47, *SD* = 0.40) had no significant

difference to medium enterprises (*M* = 4.49, *SD* = 0.43), $t(75) = -0.21, p = 0.834$.

The effect of corporate social responsibility initiatives on the financial performance of SMEs is shown in the following table:

Table 5. Effects of CSR Initiatives on SMEs' Financial Performance

R	R ²	Df	F	<i>p</i> -value
0.607	0.368	1	43.68	<.001

Note: Beta Coefficient: 0.945

Note: *R* = correlation coefficients value; *R*² = total variation in the dependent variable; *df* = degree of freedom; *F* = F-statistics

The table above shows a linear regression with a significant relationship between variables. There was a strong positive to perfect positive correlation between Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives and the financial performance of SMEs, $R^2 = 0.368, F(1) = 43.68, p < .001$. Since the beta coefficient was 0.945, corporate social responsibility initiatives can considerably affect financial performance. A unit shift in corporate social responsibility initiatives might result in a difference of up to 0.945 in their SME's financial performance. The findings also revealed that the variable's *p*-value was $0.001 < 0.05$, showing that corporate social responsibility initiatives had significant effects on the financial performance of SMEs.

Discussion

This study aimed to determine the effect of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives on the financial performance of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises. The first is about the CSR initiatives of SMEs, wherein it shows that SMEs' involvement in CSR initiatives is high by supporting various activities intended to

improve their business operation and the community they belong to. Based on the study findings, it can be concluded that SMEs are highly engaged in different CSR initiatives or activities in the communities where they operate, which will further help them retain their customers while preserving a good image of where they tend to do business. CSR emphasizes that businesses must develop ethical and sustainable business practices in the economic, social, and environmental domains to contribute to a better societal environment (Agan et al., 2016). These findings respond to the needs of SMEs to emphasize in the study of Agan et al. (2016), Brammer & Millington (2005), and Lantos (2001), which showed that SMEs engaged themselves in CSR, which helps them to attract more customers and stimulate the economy and contribute to environmental development of the community they operate.

Second, the financial performance shows that the respondents have good financial standing. A good financial performance is the one that will make a business popular. Corporate social responsibility has a good effect on a business's financial performance, as resulted in the

findings, and good financial performance can be maintained when a business knows the strategies and processes to have a good financial performance. CSR initiatives will positively affect a company's sales, reputation, and consumer perceptions (Groza, 2011; Lai, 2010). The findings, consistent with Reverte et al. (2016), find a positive and significant direct effect of the two variables wherein it provides both internal and external benefits such as investment and corporate reputation resulting to an improved relation or better employee initiatives in increasing business sales.

When the corporate social responsibility initiatives of small and medium-sized enterprises are compared, no significant difference is indicated between the CSR initiatives of small and medium-sized enterprises. Businesses only engage in socially responsible activities for moral grounds, which showed that most people cited moral and ethical considerations as reasons why CSR was significant to them (Jenkins, 2006; Longo et al., 2005). The study found that CSR is mainly used as a business strategy. Thus, CSR does not result in financial gain for the SMEs; instead, it is meant to improve their reputation.

Lastly, the effect of small and medium-sized enterprises' corporate social responsibility initiatives on their financial performance is significant. CSR is a business strategy that contributes to economic, social, and environmental development. CSR activities affect a company's financial performance, which becomes more significant as the company's environmental and social factors improve in a manner that attracts more customers. Participating in CSR initiatives will positively affect the company's sales, reputation, and consumer perceptions (Groza, 2011; Lai, 2010). The results also demonstrated that CSR initiatives had significant effects on the financial performance of SMEs.

Conclusion

This study aimed to determine the effect of corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives on the financial performance of Small and

Medium-sized Enterprises. It may be inferred that SMEs are heavily involved in various CSR initiatives in their operations, which will help them retain clients while maintaining a positive image. To contribute to a better societal environment, SMEs must create ethical and sustainable business practices in the economic, social, and environmental domains. As a result of the study findings, corporate social responsibility positively influences a business's financial performance. Good financial performance can be maintained when a business knows the methods and procedures needed to achieve good financial performance. It would appear that CSR has a significant influence on the financial performance of SMEs as it serves as a business strategy.

Furthermore, the study's unexpected findings indicate that CSR initiatives do not negatively affect or harm the financial performance of SMEs; instead, they are meant to enhance business operations. According to the findings of this study, SMEs should engage in various economic, social, and environmental activities. This activity results in establishing and maintaining an excellent business image, resulting in success in attracting new customers. Given the quick trend, CSR is always beneficial in preserving a company's image. It may not result in financial gain, but it does result in the business keeping a positive image, which leads to gaining consumers. Given this, it can be inferred that CSR indirectly affects a business's financial performance.

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are made. On a managerial level, business owners must prioritize improving the firm's performance by understanding how each aspect of CSR affects the corporate image, which draws in new customers through its economic, social, and environmental domains. It gives business owners invaluable insight into how to create strategies and strategic plans that promote sustainable development. Consequently, raising CSR performance will boost the company's success by increasing its corporate image and prospective customers. Moreover, the study demonstrated the necessity to enhance practical assistance programs to

encourage SMEs to continue their CSR implementation and their CSR performance in a sustainable manner, hence maintaining a positive corporate image that results in attracting customers. The implications of this study constitute an essential breakthrough for SMEs to strengthen CSR initiatives and improve their corporate image, ultimately leading to obtaining more customers. This analysis will shed light on the influence of all three domains on profitability obtained by SMEs.

The researchers recognize the limitations of the study relative to participants. In selecting participants, the study did not meet the required sample size since it is dependent on voluntary participation. Nevertheless, for future research, consider the number of participants. Additionally, the study only focuses on the owner or representative of the SME's point of view, creating a tendency for a biased result. Future studies should consider the triangulation method when selecting participants to consider the perception of the customers or clients on the CSR initiatives of SMEs, considering that CSR is a business strategy for SMEs to improve business operations; hence, the need for further exploration to further support the findings of this study.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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